

Research Article

“Cleaning Slippers”- Merging Comfort with Cleanliness in Shared Living Spaces

Fadli Dali^{1,*}, Ahmad Humaam A Shukor², and Iqmal Saufi Samsuri³

¹ Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 27600 Raub Campus; fadli@uitm.edu.my; 0009-0000-4531-7288

² Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 27600 Raub Campus; humaam@uitm.edu.my; 0009-0003-3717-7432

³ Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA, 27600 Raub Campus; 2022833386@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0005-2181-7276

* Correspondence: fadli@uitm.edu.my; 09-3515317.

Abstract: This abstract presents an innovative solution for maintaining cleanliness in student hostels by transforming traditional house slippers into multifunctional cleaning tools. The project addresses the challenge of restricted access to conventional cleaning appliances, such as vacuum cleaners, by integrating cleaning functionality directly into everyday footwear. Cleaning slippers provides solution to this problem by performing function as cleaning tools as well as slipper. Key features of the cleaning slippers include a detachable base that captures dust and debris and maintains user comfort. The product's affordability and dual functionality offer practical benefits for students and have shown strong market potential. The creation of cleaning slippers thereby overcoming the limitations of traditional cleaning methods in hostels environments. Their affordability, ease of use, and dual functionality make them particularly well-suited for students and other users in similar shared living conditions. Positive feedback from user testing underscores the product's effectiveness and appeal. This innovation not only meets a specific market need but also offers a scalable solution for other shared living environments. The scalable nature of this solution presents opportunities for commercialization and adaptation in diverse settings, contributing to improved hygiene and convenience in shared spaces.

Keywords: cleaning slippers, multifunctional design, student hostels

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13885756

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Maintaining cleanliness in shared living spaces, such as student hostels, presents significant challenges, particularly when conventional cleaning appliances like vacuum cleaners are prohibited (UiTM, 2019). This extended abstract introduces an innovative solution: transforming traditional house slippers into multifunctional cleaning tools. Designed specifically for students, these slippers combine comfort with practicality, addressing the need for effective cleaning solutions in restricted environments.

In conventional settings, vacuum cleaners have long been the go-to tool for maintaining cleanliness. Their efficiency in removing dust, dirt, and debris from various surfaces, including carpets and hard floors, is well-documented. Vacuum cleaners are equipped with powerful suction

mechanisms and specialized attachments that make them highly effective in deep-cleaning tasks. However, their use in student hostels or other shared spaces can be problematic. Many hostels have stringent rules that prohibit vacuum cleaners due to their size, noise levels, power consumption or even cause human injuries. The noise can affect student health such as interference with communication, hearing loss, disturbance of sleep, tinnitus, stress, annoyance, effects on performance, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, fatigue, and effects on equilibrium (Ibrahim, 2023). Walsh et al. (2022) found that there were 288 vacuum cleaner injuries (VCI) which have increasingly occurred in England and Wales between 1996–2020 and 32 children who sustained these injuries within United Kingdom regional burns service. Furthermore, the cost and maintenance of these appliances can be prohibitive for students. Students' energy saving intentions are positively related to their behaviors. Using Theory of Planned Behavior, Du and Pan (2021) found that moral norm has the greatest impact on energy saving intention, followed by perceived behavioral control and attitude. The moral norm shows students that have poor moral obligation tend to have low energy saving intention or behavior.

In contrast, the proposed multifunctional cleaning slippers offer a novel and practical alternative. These slippers are designed with embedded cleaning fibers or materials that mimic the functionality of a mop or broom. When worn, they enable users to sweep and clean floors while walking, integrating the cleaning process into daily routines. The slippers are crafted to be lightweight, comfortable, and easy to use, making them an ideal solution for environments where traditional cleaning equipment is impractical.

The cleaning slippers address several key challenges associated with traditional vacuum cleaners. Firstly, they eliminate the need for electrical outlets or batteries, making them suitable for environments where power supply might be limited or restricted. Secondly, the slippers are compact and easily stored, avoiding the bulkiness and storage issues associated with vacuum cleaners. Their design also reduces noise, an important consideration in shared living spaces where noise levels can impact the comfort of other residents.

Moreover, the multifunctional slippers are environmentally friendly, as they reduce the reliance on electricity and disposable cleaning products. By incorporating washable and reusable materials, they offer a sustainable cleaning solution that aligns with eco-friendly practices. This contrasts with vacuum cleaners, which often involve electricity consumption and generate waste through disposable filters or bags.

In summary, while traditional vacuum cleaners are highly effective for comprehensive cleaning, their limitations in restricted or shared living environments make them less ideal for certain situations. The multifunctional cleaning slippers present a practical and innovative alternative, providing students with an efficient, eco-friendly, and user-friendly solution for maintaining cleanliness in their living spaces. This approach not only addresses the practical constraints of traditional cleaning tools but also aligns with the needs and lifestyle of student residents.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Product Development/Method

The development of the cleaning slippers followed a structured process:

1. **Conceptualization:** The need for a cleaning solution in environments where traditional tools are restricted led to the idea of integrating cleaning functionality into house slippers. This concept aimed to provide a practical solution for daily cleaning tasks.
2. **Design:** The slippers feature a detachable base designed to capture and hold dust and debris. This base is constructed from a flexible, durable material with a sticky surface to trap dirt effectively. The design ensures that the slippers remain comfortable while providing necessary

cleaning functionality.

3. Prototyping: Prototypes were developed and tested to evaluate the effectiveness of the detachable base and the overall comfort of the slippers. User feedback was used to refine the design.

2.2 Materials

1. Detachable Base: Made from a flexible, durable material that adheres to the slipper's sole. This material is effective in trapping dust and debris while allowing for easy cleaning.
2. Footwear Material: Constructed from soft, breathable fabric to ensure comfort. The inner lining provides cushioning and support.

Figure 1. Cleaning slipper with detachable base.

The Figure 1 shows the sample of cleaning slippers with detachable base. The modification allows the slipper base to be detachable and replaced with a new base. It performs as a dust cleaner and hair collector.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Effectiveness of the Detachable Base

The detachable base effectively captured and retained dust and debris. Testing demonstrated its capability to trap both fine dust and larger particles such as hair. This is particularly useful for female students who are struggling with hair loss. The ease of removing and cleaning the base contributed to its practicality, ensuring that the slippers remained hygienic and functional over time.

3.2 User Comfort

User feedback indicated that the slippers were comfortable for prolonged wear. The combination of soft fabric and cushioning did not negatively impact the overall comfort, even with the integrated cleaning base.

3.3 Market Reception

Testing with a sample group of students revealed a positive reception of the product. The primary advantages highlighted were the convenience of integrating cleaning into daily routines and the affordability of RM25. This pricing was considered attractive and within budget constraints for

students. The strong interest expressed in acquiring the product suggests significant commercialization potential.

4. DISCUSSION

The cleaning slippers address a unique and pressing need in student hostels and similar shared living environments by integrating cleaning functionality into everyday footwear. This innovative approach offers a practical solution where traditional cleaning tools are restricted or impractical. In particular, the detachable base of the slippers plays a crucial role in capturing dust and debris, ensuring that the cleaning process is effective while allowing for easy maintenance and hygiene. This design feature not only enhances the slippers' functionality but also simplifies the cleaning routine, making it more manageable for students with busy schedules.

The dual functionality of the slippers—providing both comfort and cleaning capabilities—creates a distinctive market advantage. Unlike traditional cleaning tools that often require separate handling and storage, these slippers seamlessly combine the act of cleaning with the everyday activity of walking. This integration means that students can maintain cleanliness without additional effort or disruption to their daily lives. The design's emphasis on comfort ensures that users do not compromise on their ease while performing cleaning tasks, which is particularly important in environments where comfort is often a priority.

Positive user feedback and strong market interest underscore the slippers' potential for commercialization. Early adopters have praised the slippers for their practicality and effectiveness, highlighting their value in environments where conventional cleaning tools are either banned or inconvenient to use. Furthermore, there is a demand for environmentally-friendly products especially among consumers that have a strong attitude toward environmental awareness and have strong health consciousness (Pathange et al, 2024; Tamboli 2023). The affordable price point of the slippers makes them accessible to a broad range of students, who are often budget-conscious and looking for cost-effective solutions to maintain their living spaces. The practical benefits, combined with the product's affordability, enhance its appeal within this demographic.

Furthermore, the concept of cleaning slippers is not limited to student hostels. Its potential application extends to other shared living situations, such as dormitories, communal housing, and even residential care facilities. In these environments, where traditional cleaning tools may also face restrictions or where ease of use is paramount, the slippers offer a versatile solution that could significantly improve cleanliness and convenience. This broader applicability enhances the market potential of the product, suggesting that it could find a place in various sectors beyond student accommodations.

Overall, the cleaning slippers represent an innovative advancement in maintaining cleanliness in shared living spaces. By merging the functionality of cleaning with the practicality of everyday footwear, they offer a solution that aligns with the needs of modern users while overcoming the limitations of traditional cleaning tools. As such, they hold considerable promise for both commercial success and widespread adoption.

5. CONCLUSION

The cleaning slippers successfully address the challenge of maintaining cleanliness in environments with restricted access to conventional cleaning appliances. Their innovative design, combining a detachable base with comfortable footwear, offers a practical and effective solution. The

positive findings from user testing and the strong market interest underscore the product's potential for commercialization and broader adoption in shared living spaces.

Acknowledgements: We would like to thank the academic staff of the Faculty of Business and Management at Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Pahang, Raub Campus, for allowing us to collaborate with their students enrolled MGT315 Creative and Critical Thinking. Special thanks to Nurfarisa Athira binti Abd Rahman, Wan Nur Asha binti Wan Zakaria, Hanisah binti Rosman, Nurul Najwatul Najihah binti Zulkurnain and Iqmal Saufi bin Samsuri for their early works and contributions. Special thanks also to UiTM Kelantan for organizing the third Virtual International 3-Minute Business Idea Pitch & Innovation Competition (3MPIC2024).

References

- Du, J & Pan, W (2021). Examining energy saving behaviors in student dormitories using an expanded theory of planned behavior. *Habitat International*, vol. 107, p. 102308. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2020.102308>
- Ibrahim, S. (2023). Reviewing the effects of noise pollution on students (college and university). *Al-Kadhum 2nd International Conference on Modern Applications of Information and Communication Technology (AIP Conference Proceedings)* 2591, 030056 <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0121878>
- Pathange, R., Parcha, R., Ara, I., Anusha, I., Fatima, I. & Fathima, J. (2024). A Study on Consumer Purchase Behavior Towards Green Products. *International Research Journal on Advanced Engineering and Management*, 2(4), pp. 913-922.
- Tamboli, A., Haque, M., Jojare, Y. & Ohol, A. (2023). Consumer Preference for Eco-Friendly Products in Relation to Sustainability Awareness. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44 (5-6), pp. 87-93
- UiTM (2019). Buku Panduan & Peraturan Kolej Kediaman Pelajar, Unit Pengurusan Kolej Dahlia & Tualang. Pusat Asasi Cawangan Selangor, Kampus Dengkil. Available Online at <https://asasi.uitm.edu.my/web/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/PANDUAN-KOLEJ.pdf>
- Walsh, K., Osman-Elabd, M., Sheikh, Z., & Soueid, A. Vacuum cleaner friction injuries in paediatrics: A 10 year review of national trends, *Burns*, 48 (4), pp. 1013-1018